

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Occurrence of epigenetic resistance

SPOKE 6 - PRIMARY AGROINDUSTRY

Flagship Project VINO

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR's Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR's Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR's Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the results of the controlled growth and herbicide application trials performed in collaboration with SAGEA® Group company and of the analysis of herbicide resistance phenomena surveyed in vineyards of Oltrepò Pavese.

Controlled growth and herbicide application trials made it possible to identify the susceptible (SUS) and resistant biotypes (RES), which were further analyzed.

The herbicide resistances resulting from DNA mutations (Target Site Resistances - TSR), those resulting from metabolic processes of herbicide detoxification, herbicide isolation or reduced herbicide uptake (Non-Target Site Resistance - NTSR) and those involving microRNA-mediated post-transcriptional regulation of the expression of genes encoding enzymes involved in NTSR (i.e. cytochromes P450, aldo-keto-reductase, ABC transporters, ...) were studied and characterized.

A) Controlled growth and herbicide application trials

Applied methodology and results of controlled growth and herbicide application trials.
Distinction of glyphosate susceptible and resistant biotypes

Analysis of sensitivity/resistance of plants to glyphosate

Three weeks after treatment (21 days), the sensitivity/resistance of *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) P. Beauv, *Sorghum halepense* (L.) Pers., *Coryza canadensis* Cronq and *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers. to glyphosate was tested through visual inspection in comparison to reference samples (dose 0X), following European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization (EPPO) standards [1,2]. Growth tests thus made it possible to identify the susceptible (SUS) and resistant biotypes (RES) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Analysis of sensitivity / resistance of plants to glyphosate. A,B: SUS and RES biotype of *E. crus-galli*. C,D: SUS and RES biotype of *S. halepense*. E,F: SUS and RES biotype of *C. canadensis*. G,H: SUS and RES biotype of *C. dactylon*.

All tested weeds exhibited resistance towards glyphosate.

In the H panel of Figure 1 , the red circle indicates a recovery phenomenon recorded for *C. dactylon* at the 21st day after treatment. Two weeks later the specimen continued its growth, exhibiting resistance toward the application of glyphosate (Figure 2).

Figure 2: resistant *C. dactylon* specimen at the 21st day after treatment.

B) Analysis of herbicide resistance occurrence

Applied methodology and results of the analysis of herbicide resistance phenomena.
Distinction of TSRs, NTSRs and of microRNAs involved in post-transcriptional regulation of the expression of genes encoding enzymes acting in herbicide detoxification

Bioinformatic analysis

For all the weeds analyzed, genes involved in herbicide resistance (i.e. herbicide detoxification, isolation) were selected to be tested on the basis of previously published studies [3-12].

Starting from the complete coding sequence of the selected genes, mature miRNAs with a sequence complementarity rate $\geq 80\%$ with the target gene were predicted in silico using the psRNATarget: A Plant Small RNA Target Analysis web server (Schema V2, 2017 release) [13-15].

The predicted miRNAs and the respective genes target are listed by species in table 1, 2, 3 and 4.

Table 1: miRNAs and genes selected for expression analysis in *E. crus-galli*. A.n.: accession number

<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>			
miRNA	miRNA a.n.	gene	Gene a.n.
sbi-miR169q	MIMAT0014044	EPSPS	HQ436353.1
sbi-miR162	MIMAT0014041	ABCC8	MT249005.1
sbi-miR5564c-5p	MIMAT0026390	ABCC10	MT249006.1
osa-miR5490	MIMAT0022123	AKR4-1	MK592097
osa-miR5154	MIMAT0021104	AKR4-2	MK592098

Table 2: miRNAs and genes selected for expression analysis in *S. halepense*. A.n.: accession number

<i>Sorghum halepense</i>			
miRNA	miRNA a.n.	gene	Gene a.n.
sbi-miR169q	MIMAT0014044	EPSPS	HQ436353.1
sbi-miR6223-5p	MIMAT0026412	SbABCB9	NP_182223.1
sbi-miR5565f	MIMAT0022244	SbABCB4	NM_130268.4.1
sbi-miR821c	MIMAT0011387	AKR4C10	XM_002456588.2

Table 3: miRNAs and genes selected for expression analysis in *C. canadensis*. A.n.: accession number

<i>Conyza canadensis</i>			
miRNA	miRNA a.n.	gene	Gene a.n.
ath-miR834	MIMAT0004254	EPSPS	AY545666.1
ath-miR418	MIMAT0001326	ABCM10	NM_130347.4
ath-miR2934-3p	MIMAT0020364	ABCM11	NM_112148.3
ath-miR8121	MIMAT0032262	CAT4	NM_001161114.2

Table 4: miRNAs and genes selected for expression analysis in *C. dactylon*. A.n.: accession number

<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>			
miRNA	miRNA a.n.	gene	Gene a.n.
sbi-miR169q	MIMAT0014044	EPSPS	HQ436353.1

osa-miR2097-3p	MIMAT0010059	CYPNZ1	KT184658.1
osa-miR5837.2	MIMAT0023313	CYPNZ2	KT184659.1

Analysis of TSR

The presence of the missense mutation at the codon Pro106, attributable to target site resistance (TSR) for glyphosate, was investigated in all RES biotypes of *E. crus-galli*, *S. halepense*, *C. canadensis* and *C. dactylon* by restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) analysis.

None of the specimens analyzed exhibited the presence of the missense mutation at codon Pro106: all the specimens were wild type at the EPSPS gene. Thus, resistance to glyphosate was not identified as TSR.

Figure 3 shows an example of an electrophoretic trace in which it can be seen on the left of the 100 bp marker the successful amplification of the EPSPS gene and on the right of the 100 bp marker the successful digestion of the EPSPS gene with the HaeIII endonuclease for each of the samples analyzed, indicating wild type genotypes.

Figure 3: amplification and digestion of the EPSPS gene in samples of *E. crus-galli*

Analysis of NTSR and of microRNAs involved in post-transcriptional regulation of the expression of genes encoding enzymes acting in herbicide detoxification

The presence of a microRNA-mediated post-transcriptional regulation of the expression of enzymes involved in herbicide resistance was investigated in SUS and RES biotypes of *E. crus-galli*, *S. halepense*, *C. canadensis* and *C. dactylon* by relative real-time quantitative PCR (RT-qPCR). The comparative Ct method ($2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method) by Livak and Schmittgen (2001) was used to calculate the expression levels of genes and miRNAs [16].

An epigenetic regulation in which the miRNAs listed in tables 1, 2, 3 and 4 are involved was recorded in all the weeds analyzed.

Results concerning genes and miRNAs targeting their transcripts in *E. crus-galli* are reported in Figure 4.

Figure 4.: Expression levels of the miRNAs studied (orange) and the mRNA of their target genes (blue) in susceptible (SUS) and resistant (RES) biotypes of *E. crus-galli* before and after glyphosate treatment.

As shown in Figures 4A, 4B and 4C, after spraying with glyphosate, in the SUS biotype, genes expression slightly increased, while that of the respective miRNAs slightly decreased. The same relationship between genes expression and miRNAs is found in the RES biotypes, but the rate of increase in genes expression is higher.

The expression of AKR4-1 (Figure 4D) showed a high level (> 2.00) in the RES biotype before glyphosate application. After herbicide treatment, AKR4-1 expression decreased in both SUS and RES biotypes, despite the fold level in RES remained high (> 2.00). Osa-miR5490 transcription rose in both SUS and RES biotypes after herbicide application, but in this latter not enough to counteract the expression of the gene.

As shown in Figure 4E, after spraying with glyphosate, in the SUS biotype the expression of AKR-4 and osa-miR5154 slightly increased. The same relationship between gene expression and miRNAs is found in the RES biotype, but the rate of increase in ARK-4 expression is higher.

Results concerning genes and miRNAs targeting their transcripts in *S. halepense* are reported in Figure 5.

Figure 5: . Expression levels of the miRNAs studied (orange) and the mRNA of their target genes (blue) in susceptible (SUS) and resistant (RES) biotypes of *S. halepense* before and after glyphosate treatment.

As shown in Figures 5A, 5B and 5C, after spraying with glyphosate, genes expression slightly decreased in the SUS biotype, while increased in the RES one. After treatment, miRNAs transcription remained almost equal in SUS biotype. In the RES biotype *sbi-miR169q* transcription remained unaltered, while that of *sbi-miR6223-5p* and *sbi-miR5565f* decreased upon glyphosate treatment.

The expression of *AKR4C10* (Figure 5D) showed a high level (> 2.00) in the RES biotype before glyphosate application. After herbicide treatment, *AKR4C10* expression decreased in both SUS and RES biotypes, despite the fold level in the RES remained high (> 2.00). *Sbi-miR821c* transcription rose in both SUS and RES biotypes after herbicide application, but in these latter not enough to counteract the expression of the gene.

Results concerning genes and miRNAs targeting their transcripts in *C. canadensis* are reported in Figure 6.

Figure 6: . Expression levels of the miRNAs studied (orange) and the mRNA of their target genes (blue) in susceptible (SUS) and resistant (RES) biotypes of *C. canadensis* before and after glyphosate treatment.

As shown in Figures 6A, after spraying with glyphosate, in the SUS biotype EPSPS expression slightly increased, while in the RES one sharply rise. Upon treatment, *ath-miR834* transcription slightly decreased in both biotypes.

Upon glyphosate application, in the SUS biotype EPSPS expression slightly decreased, while in the RES one sharply rise. Upon treatment, *ath-miR418* transcription slightly increased in both

biotypes. In the RES biotype, miRNA expression recorded high values (> 2.00) both before and after treatment: nevertheless resulted not enough to counteract the expression of the gene upon herbicide administration (Figure 6B).

After spraying with glyphosate, in the SUS biotype ABCM11 expression slightly increased, while in RES one sharply rise. Upon treatment, ath-miR2934-3p transcription increased in the SUS biotype, counteracting ABCM11 expression, thus sensitizing the weed toward the herbicide. In the RES biotype the transcription of miRNA remained almost equal before and after treatment (Figure 6C).

The expression of CAT4 (Figure 6D) showed a high level (> 2.00) in the RES biotype before glyphosate application. After herbicide treatment, CAT4 expression sharply decreased in the SUS biotype, while in the RES one CAT4 expression level remained high (> 2.00), while recording a decrease. The transcription of ath-miR8121 sharply rose in both SUS and RES biotypes after glyphosate spraying, but in this latter not enough to counteract the expression of CAT4.

Results concerning genes and miRNAs targeting their transcripts in *C. dactylon* are reported in Figure 7.

Figure 7: . Expression levels of the miRNAs studied (orange) and the mRNA of their target genes (blue) in susceptible (SUS) and resistant (RES) biotypes of *C. dactylon* before and after glyphosate treatment.

As shown in Figure 7A, upon glyphosate administration, in the SUS biotype EPSPS expression sharply decreased, while in the RES one sharply rise. Upon treatment, *sbi-miR169q* transcription sharply increased in the SUS biotype (> 2.00), counteracting the expression of EPSPS gene. In the RES biotype, upon treatment *sbi-miR169q* transcription recorded a light increase, but the miRNA remained under-expressed (< 2.00), resulting not enough to inhibit the expression of EPSPS gene upon herbicide administration.

Upon glyphosate application, *CYPN21* and *CYPN22* expressions recorded a slight increase (< 2.00) in the SUS biotype and a sharp rise (> 2.00) in the RES one (Figures 7B and 7C). The transcription of *osa-miR2097-3p* recorded a light decrease in the SUS biotype and a sharp reduction in the RES one, after treatment (Figure 7B). *Osa-miR5837.2* transcription resulted triggered by herbicide spraying and raised up in both SUS and RES biotypes (Figure 7C): in this latter, the expression of the miRNA resulted not enough to inhibit the expression of *CYPN22*.

Conclusive remarks

To sum up, a microRNA-mediated post-transcriptional regulation of the expression of enzymes involved in herbicide resistance was recorded in all the investigated weeds.

In susceptible biotypes miRNAs transcription, triggered by glyphosate treatment, down-regulated the expression of target genes involved in herbicide detoxification, sensitizing the plant to the treatment. On the other hand, in the resistant biotypes the miRNAs transcription triggered by the herbicide treatment resulted not high enough to down-regulate the expression of the genes responsible for resistance: this allowed the plant to survive the herbicide application.

In light of these findings and considering that miRNAs can be activated in plants by a variety of environmental factors, including abiotic stressors (i.e. heat [17], cold [18], drought [19], salinity [20] herbicides [21]) or biotic interactions (i.e. soil microbial communities [22]) that lead to the exhibition of a stress response enabling the organism to tolerate ecological conditions, it is pivotal to investigate the environmental factors that can affect miRNAs transcription in order to manage the occurrence of herbicide resistance. Furthermore, the prosecution of these analyses may be useful to gain information about the whole complex of miRNAs able to counteract the expression of genes coding enzymes involved in herbicide resistance in weeds whose genome and miRNAome have not been sequenced yet. This would provide a deeper understanding of epigenetic regulatory processes, which could be exploited to manage herbicide resistance in a more sustainable way.

For example, if the weed-miRNA complexes regulating genes involved in herbicide resistance were known, it would be possible to synthesize miRNA-based bio-herbicides, increasing the efficacy of treatments and decreasing the impact on the environment and human health.

Similarly, if environmental factors triggering the transcription of miRNAs involved in the silencing of genes responsible for herbicide resistance were recognized, it would be possible to predict the occurrence of resistance through the mapping of the soil characteristics of agricultural fields,

thus adopting a pro-active and more sustainable approach in the management of this phytosanitary problem.

Publications and scientific activity

1. Cusaro, C. M., Capelli, E., Picco, A. M., Grazioli, C., & Brusoni, M. (2023). Herbicide stress-induced miRNAs transcription changes in resistance *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) P. Beauv. biotypes. Acts of the 2nd Conference of Young Botanists (CYBO 2023), Newsletter of the Italian Botanical Society, 7(1), 102.
2. Cusaro, C. M., Parisi, N., & Brusoni, M. (2023). SOS herbicide resistances in vineyards. Book of Abstracts XIV International Scientific Agriculture Symposium "AGROSYM 2023", 292. Jahorina, 5/8 October 2023.
3. Cusaro, C. M., Capelli, E., Picco, A. M., & Brusoni, M. (2024). Incidence of resistance to ALS and ACCase inhibitors in *Echinochloa* species and soil microbial composition in Northern Italy. Scientific reports, 14(1), 10544. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-59856-0>
4. Cusaro, C. M., Parisi, N., Franci, E., & Brusoni, M. (2024). Glyphosate resistance in the vineyards in Oltrepo Pavese (Italy): The case of *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) P. Beauv. Book of Abstracts XV International Scientific Agriculture Symposium "AGROSYM 2024" (p. 325). Jahorina, 10/13 October 2024.
5. Cusaro, C. M., Capelli, E., Picco, A. M., & Brusoni, M. (2025). Herbicide resistance and soil microbial composition. Acts of the 3rd Conference of Young Botanists (CYBO 2025). Newsletter of the Italian Botanical Society. The book of abstract is not yet available.
6. Cusaro, C. M., Capelli, E., Picco, A. M., Guarise, M., Gozio, E., Zarpellon, P., & Brusoni, M. (2025). MicroRNA-Mediated Post-Transcriptional Regulation of Enzymes Involved in Herbicide Resistance in *Echinochloa oryzicola* (Vasinger) Vasinger. Plants, 14(5), 719. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants14050719>

References

1. EPPO. Efficacy evaluation of herbicides: Weeds in water-seeded rice. Bulletin 2011, 41, 282–285.
2. EPPO Database on PPI Standards. Available online: <https://ppi.eppo.int/standards/PP1-062-3>
3. Pan, L., Yu, Q., Han, H., Mao, L., Nyporko, A., Fan, L., Bai, L., & Powles, S. (2019). Aldo-keto Reductase Metabolizes Glyphosate and Confers Glyphosate Resistance in *Echinochloa colona*. *Plant physiology*, 181(4), 1519–1534. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.19.00979>
4. Dalazen, G., Markus, C., & Merotto, A., Jr. (2018). Differential expression of genes associated with degradation enhancement of imazethapyr in barnyardgrass (*Echinochloa crus-galli*). *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 10, 389–401. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jas.v10n9p389>
5. Tani, E., Chachalis, D., & Travlos, I. S. (2015). Glyphosate resistance mechanism in *Conyza canadensis* involves synchronization of EPSPS and ABC-transporter genes. *Plant Molecular Biology Reporter*, 33(6), 1721–1730. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11105-015-0868-8>
6. Nol, N., Tsikou, D., Eid, M., Livieratos, I. C., & Giannopolitis, C. N. (2012). Shikimate leaf disc assay for early detection of glyphosate resistance in *Conyza canadensis* and relative transcript levels of EPSPS and ABC transporter genes. *Weed Research*, 52(3), 233–241. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3180.2012.00911.x>
7. Moretti, M. L., Alarcón-Reverte, R., Pearce, S., Morran, S., & Hanson, B. D. (2017). Transcription of putative tonoplast transporters in response to glyphosate and paraquat stress in *Conyza bonariensis* and *Conyza canadensis* and selection of reference genes for qRT-PCR. *PLOS ONE*, 12(7), e0180794. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0180794>
8. Zheng, T., Yu, X., Sun, Y., Zhang, Q., Zhang, X., Tang, M., Lin, C., & Shen, Z. (2022). Expression of a cytochrome P450 gene from Bermuda grass *Cynodon dactylon* in soybean confers tolerance to multiple herbicides. *Plants*, 11(7), 949. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants11070949>
9. Guo, Z., Yuan, X., Li, L., Zeng, M., Yang, J., Tang, H., & Duan, C. (2022). Genome-Wide Analysis of the ATP-Binding Cassette (ABC) Transporter Family in *Zea mays* L. and Its Response to Heavy Metal Stresses. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 23(4), 2109. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23042109>
10. Vila-Aiub, M. M., Balbi, M. C., Distéfano, A. J., Fernández, L., Hopp, E., Yu, Q., & Powles, S. B. (2012). Glyphosate resistance in perennial Sorghum halepense (Johnsongrass), endowed by reduced glyphosate translocation and leaf uptake. *Pest management science*, 68(3), 430–436. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.2286>
11. Fernández, L., de Haro, L. A., Distefano, A. J., Carolina Martínez, M., Lía, V., Papa, J. C., Olea, I., Tosto, D., & Esteban Hopp, H. (2013). Population genetics structure of glyphosate-resistant Johnsongrass (*Sorghum halepense* L. Pers) does not support a single origin of the resistance. *Ecology and evolution*, 3(10), 3388–3400. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.671>
12. Vazquez-García, J. C., Palma-Bautista, C., Rojano-Delgado, A. M., De Prado, R., & Menendez, J. (2020). The First Case of Glyphosate Resistance in Johnsongrass (*Sorghum halepense* (L.) Pers.) in Europe. *Plants (Basel, Switzerland)*, 9(3), 313. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants9030313>
13. Dai, X.; Zhao, P.X. psRNATarget: A plant small RNA target analysis server. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2011, 39, W155–W159.
14. Dai, X.; Zhuang, Z.; Zhao, P.X. Computational analysis of miRNA targets in plants: Current status and challenges. *Brief. Bioinform.* 2011, 12, 115–121.
15. Dai, X.; Zhuang, Z.; Zhao, P.X. psRNATarget: A plant small RNA target analysis server (2017 release). *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2018, 46, W49–W54.
16. Livak, K. J., & Schmittgen, T. D. (2001). Analysis of relative gene expression data using real-time quantitative PCR and the 2^{-ΔΔCT} method. *Methods*, 25(4), 402–408. <https://doi.org/10.1006/meth.2001.1262>
17. Pegler, J.L.; Oultram, J.M.J.; Grof, C.P.L.; Eamens, A.L. Profiling the Abiotic Stress Responsive microRNA Landscape of *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Plants* 2019, 8, 58.
18. Zhao, W.; Xiao, W.; Sun, J.; Chen, M.; Ma, M.; Cao, Y.; Cen, W.; Li, R.; Luo, J. An Integration of MicroRNA and Transcriptome Sequencing Analysis Reveal Regulatory Roles of miRNAs in Response to Chilling Stress in Wild Rice. *Plants* 2022, 11, 977.
19. Guo, Y.; Zhao, S.; Zhu, C.; Chang, X.; Yue, C.; Wang, Z.; Lin, Y.; Lai, Z. Identification of drought-responsive miRNAs and physiological characterization of tea plant (*Camellia sinensis* L.) under drought stress. *BMC Plant Biol.* 2017, 17, 211.
20. Váakf±r, O.; Arf±kan, B.; Karpuz, B.; Turgut-Kara, N. Expression analysis of miRNAs and their targets related to salt stress in *Solanum lycopersicum* H-2274. *Biotechnol. Biotechnol. Equip.* 2021, 35, 275–282.
21. Cusaro, C.M.; Grazioli, C.; Capelli, E.; Picco, A.M.; Guarise, M.; Gozio, E.; Zarpellon, P.; Brusoni, M. Involvement of miRNAs in Metabolic Herbicide Resistance to Bispyribac-Sodium in *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) P. Beauv. *Plants* 2022, 11, 3359.
22. Cusaro, C. M., Capelli, E., Picco, A. M., & Brusoni, M. (2024). Incidence of resistance to ALS and ACCase inhibitors in *Echinochloa* species and soil microbial composition in Northern Italy. *Scientific reports*, 14(1), 10544. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-59856-0>